

The Influence of Temptation on Female Preferences for Premium Personal Care Products

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ABSTRACT

Temptation is a powerful and complex force that plays a significant role in human behaviour and decision-making. Female temptation during selection of premium personal care products (PPCPs) is driven by a complex interplay of factors that extend beyond basic products attributes. This temptation is not merely a result of the product's functional benefits but is deeply rooted in the symbolic and experiential value that premium products offer. This study investigates the factors contributing to female temptation during the selection of premium personal care products, utilizing Exploratory Factors Analysis (EFA) and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) through Smart PLS. The research aims to identify and quantify the underlying constructs that influence purchasing decisions in this market segment. EFA is employed to uncover the key dimensions of temptation, revealing factors conspicuousness, status consumption, brand-name consciousness, and need for uniqueness. These factors are then modelled using smart PLS to examine the relationship between them and their impact on female temptation during selection of PPCPs and its impact on willingness to pay a premium price. The result indicates that all factors are the most significant drivers of temptation, leading to a higher willingness to pay a premium price. The study provides a robust framework for understanding the complex dynamics of female temptation in PPCPs and while price sensitivity is acknowledged, it is frequently outweighed by the female temptation to premium brands.

Keywords: Conspicuousness, Brand-name consciousness, Female temptation, Status, Premium personal care products, Consumption, Willingness to pay.

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INTRODUCTION

According to Hoch and Loewenstein (1991), these choices include a struggle between desire and self-control to determine whether a person gives in to their inclinations. Temptation, in the context of consumer behaviour, refers to the allure or attraction that certain products hold, compelling individuals to make purchases that may not be entirely rational but are driven by desire, emotions, and perceived self-worth. In the realm of premium personal care products, this temptation is heightened by sophisticated marketing strategies, luxurious packaging, and the promise of exclusivity and superior results. For female consumers, the process of selecting these PPCPs is often influenced by a complex interplay of emotional and psychological factors. Among these, the concept of “temptation” plays a crucial role, driving purchasing decisions that are often beyond mere functional needs. It also refers to alluring appeal and irresistible desire that PPCPs can evoke. These products often promise not just functional benefits but also an enhanced sense of well-being, confidence, and luxury, making them particularly tempting to female consumers. The allure of sophisticated packing, the prestige of renowned brands, and the promise of superior results all contribute to the temptation experienced during the purchase decision.

This study seeks to explore the various dimensions of temptation that influence female consumers when selecting PPCPs. By examining factors conspicuousness, status consumption, brand-name consciousness, and need for uniqueness. By delving into the underlying psychological mechanisms that drive female temptation in the context of premium personal care products, this research will provide valuable insights for marketers, brand managers, and product developers. Understanding these dynamics can lead to more effective marketing strategies that resonate with the target audience, ultimately influencing purchase decisions and brand loyalty.

LITERATURE REVIEW

MacDonald et al (2020) in the study examined the effect of lipstick by analysing women's expenditure on cosmetics products. The study revealed that women have shifted towards the substitute from higher price to lower price products. The increase occurred as it increased the chances of staying back or being employed during the economic downturn. Rather, we contend

that younger women spend less on other categories like dining out, jewellery, and clothing to buy more cosmetics.

SueLin (2010) in the study examined the consumers' decision-making processes and has been ongoing to understand better the variables that affect and shape consumers' decisions and mental processes. This article employs two alternative models to analyse the drivers of personal grooming product usage because the traditional consumer black box model could not give a thorough understanding of the consumer's mind. The foundational elements of the Hawkins, Best, and Coney and Engel, Kollat, and Blackwell models are first examined in this paper. The importance of emotions in consumers' decision-making process is examined in light of this. Finally, the elements influencing cosmetics use are explored, showing how the various factors relate to the different categories based on consumer models.

Roberts et al (2015) in the study has analysed the two-consumer behaviour: impulse buying and compulsive buying, and tested the impact of satisfaction with life (SWL), self-control (SC), and core self-evaluation (CSE) on impulse buying (IB) and compulsive buying (CB). Adults and students' sample has been taken and empirically tested. The result revealed that SC has negative impact on IB and CB, but its association with the two behaviour varies. SC has a positive association with SWL in both samples. CSE has a positive impact on SC and has a negative impact on IB and CB. SWL has not impacted IB and CB. Partial association between CSE and SC has been made by the SC for adults and partially impact of CSE on CB for adults but have no impact on students.

Ravishankar et al () in study has revealed that beauty firms thrive on social media in an era when technology permeates every aspect of life. Brands are increasingly using Instagram marketing to attract and persuade new customers. The current thesis focuses on Instagram's impact on social media and the organic beauty sector, with a detailed examination of the market and female consumers. The objective is to comprehend how Instagram content influences consumers' choices and what characteristics aid Instagram in crafting the ideal message to advertise organic beauty products. Different facets of Instagram content, such as the organic beauty market, educational content, influencer follower relationships, brand-follower relationships, and differences between marketing and product promotion, must be considered to reach consistent conclusions. In two steps, this study examines the acceptance of organic

beauty products among young women. To determine whether Indian Organic beauty firms have established themselves in the Instagram community and to carefully review whether Instagram marketing has a sizable impact on young women's decisions to purchase Indian Organic beauty goods.

Deshpande (2015) in study concluded that developed nations are turning to Ayurveda for treatments to restore their citizens' wellness due to the lack of a cure for chronic diseases and the adverse side effects of conventional medications. Evidence-based practice is largely what drives modern medicine. Traditional remedies have a long history that has been passed down through years of experience, so they are certain to contain some essential substances as well as those that are no longer effective. The treatments associated with Ayurvedic massages, herbal therapy, yoga, and conventional surgery are quickly attracting everyone's attention and look to be the future of health and wellbeing. The growing body of research showing the adverse side effects of contemporary synthetic goods is thought to be the cause of this revived interest in herbal remedies. To compete in the global market and satisfy customers, systematic dissemination of scientific information about Ayurvedic/herbal medicines is required. Given the rising desire for natural remedies, ayurveda has a bright future in India as a company.

Ulfat et al (2014) examined the association between recurrent purchase decisions and brand equity of females by linear regression analysis. This study is based on Aakers' brand equity model. It gives the perception of female consumers about brand loyalty, brand quality, brand association, and brand awareness. It can be used by the worldwide manufacturers of beauty care products whose products are demanded by Pakistan's local products.

OBJECTIVES

1. To study the impact of socio-psychological factors on female temptation during selection of premium personal care products.
2. To analysis the impact of female temptation during selection of premium personal care products on willingness to pay a premium price.

CONCEPTUAL MODEL AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

We develop a conceptual model that is shown in Figure 1 and related hypotheses for experimental research.

1. *Conspicuousness and female temptation during selection of premium personal care products (PPCPs).*

According to Ferraro et al. (2013), "situations in which a consumer blatantly draws attention to the brand, such as by flaunting," are reflected in the concept of conspicuousness. One of the main variables influencing luxury consumption is thought to be conspicuous consumption, which is the act of displaying one's wealth through the acquisition of products or services (Janssen et al., 2017). Mason (1992) developed the conspicuous consumption theory, which associates premium products with the ostentatious display of wealth. The others studies have taken the traditional luxury perspective to explore conspicuousness (Hwang et al., 2014; Janssen et al., 2017), this study investigates whether brand conspicuousness affects female behaviour to buy PPCPs and is willing to pay a premium price as well.

H1: *Conspicuousness is positively associated with female temptation during selection of PPCPs.*

Fig 1. Conceptual Model

2. *Status consumption and female temptation during selection of PPCPs.*

Status consumption and consumer perceptions of reasonably priced luxury "The motivational process by which individuals strive to improve their social standing through status consumption of consumer products that confer or symbolize status for both the individual and surrounding others" is how Eastman et al. (1999) define status consumption. They rely on buying luxury brands to conform to social standards, which is in line with the social comparison theory, which holds that people often adopt the viewpoint of the majority in their reference

groups (Wiedmanet al., 2009). Since consumers buy luxury products to follow trends and project a certain status to their social circles, status is often thought to influence their behaviour when it comes to consuming luxury goods (Kim and Jang, 2014). The combination of status appeal and temptation can lead to impulse buying, where women might make unplanned purchase due to the immediate allure of the products. The need to maintain or enhance social status can make premium products particularly tempting, as they not only fulfil functional needs but also serve as symbols of achievement. The allure of premium, combined with the desire to signal status, can create a compelling reason for female temptation to choose these products, often leading to indulgent and sometimes impulsive purchases. H2: *Status Consumption is positively associated with female temptation during selection of PPCPs.*

3. *Brand-name consciousness and female temptation during selection of PPCPs.*

According to Nelson and McLeod (2005), brand consciousness is the psychological alignment of brand names in consumers' purchasing actions. As a result, people with high brand consciousness will rather buy well-known brands than unknown ones (Giovannini et al., 2015; Liao and Wang, 2009). In line with this, we contend that reasonably priced luxury goods, similar to other well-known brand-name goods, aid in the socialization process, self-expression, and group identification of price-conscious, brand-conscious consumers (Kavkani et al., 2011; Sharda and Bhat, 2019). If a brand is popular or highly regarded among peers, women may feel a stronger temptation to purchase products from that brand to maintain social standing. Brand name consciousness and female temptation are intertwined in driving female behaviour in the premium personal care market. Female who are conscious of brand name are more likely to be tempted by the allure of premium products, often resulting in purchase driven by both emotional and social factors.

H3: *Brand Name Consciousness is positively associated with female temptation during selection of PPCPs.*

4. *Need for uniqueness and female temptation*

In order to create and improve one's self-image and social image, customers' need for uniqueness is defined as a "trait of pursuing differentness relative to others; achieved through

acquisition, utilization, and disposition of consumer goods" (Tian et al., 2001). According to the social comparison hypothesis, situations that put a customer's sense of uniqueness in jeopardy activate their urge to feel different from others. Through self-identifying behaviours and activities, these customers try to regain their sense of self-worth and reduce negative emotions (Tian et al., 2001). One of the behaviours that customers who feel a higher need for uniqueness value the most is the display of differentiation through the consumption of luxury goods (Belk, 1988). Women with a high need for uniqueness are likely to be especially tempted by rare or exclusive premium personal care products. The scarcity of these products can heighten their allure, making them difficult to resist. The need for uniqueness and female temptation are deeply connected in the context of premium personal care products. Female with a strong desire to stand out are likely to be tempted by the products that offer uniqueness, exclusivity, and the opportunity for self-expression.

H4: Need for uniqueness is positively associated with female temptation during selection of PPCPs.

5. Female Temptation during selection of PPCPs and willingness to pay a premium price.

When consumers are willing to pay more for a brand's products than they are for comparable products from other relevant brands, the brand commands a higher price (Aaker, 1996). From a conceptual standpoint, price premiums are considered by a number of authors to be the most valuable measure of brand equity (Blackston, 1995; Aaker, 1996; Sethuraman, 2000). Their theory appears to be supported empirically by a number of studies (Agarwal and Rao, 1996; Ailawadi et al., 2003), which demonstrate, for instance, that a price premium is a strong predictor of market shares and is relatively consistent over time, while also capturing variations in the health of the brand. The intersection of premium, quality, brand name and status create a potent mix that drives women to invest in high-end personal care items.

H5: Female Temptation during selection of PPCPs is positively associated with willingness to pay a premium price.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The data for this study were gathered from a questionnaire survey given a variety of premium products buyers in Uttar Pradesh, India. This includes skin care products, hair care products and body care products. Snowball sampling was used to collect information from consumers and purchasers of reasonably priced luxury brands after employing some contacts through personal recommendations and a university alumni organisation. A total of 350 questionnaires were sent out; 250 of those were returned. The response that was received were carefully reviewed in order to remove those that could not be analysed. 236 useful replies were then judged appropriate for additional examination.

The primary constructions of this research were assessed using pre-existing scales that were administered on five-point Likert scales ranging from 1 for “strongly agree” to 5 for “strongly disagree”.

This study employs a quantitative research methodology combining Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) using Smart PLS. The methodology is structured to explore underlying factors in the data and to test hypothesized relationship between constructs.

DATA ANALYSIS AND RESULT

Exploratory factor analysis (EFA), reliability and validity analyses

EFA is conducted to identify the underlying factor structure of the dataset and to reduce the dimensionality by grouping related variables into factors. KMO statistic is a measure used to assess the adequacy of sample for conducting factor analysis. It examines whether the variables in the dataset are sufficiently correlated to warrant the application of factor analysis. In this case, the KMO value is 0.776, which is considered suitable for factor analysis. Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity tests the null hypothesis that the correlation matrix is an identity matrix. Since the significance level (p-value = 0.000) is less than 0.005, we reject the null hypothesis.

Table 1 KMO and Bartlett’s Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.776
Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2087.423
	df	171
	Sig.	.000

Table 2 presents the results from a factor analysis, focusing on how much variance in the data is explained by each extracted factors or component. The pattern continues, with the first six components explaining a total of 71.022% of the variance.

Table 2 Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings ^a
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total
1	5.674	29.865	29.865	5.674	29.865	29.865	4.018
2	2.211	11.639	41.504	2.211	11.639	41.504	3.071
3	1.839	9.676	51.180	1.839	9.676	51.180	3.859
4	1.426	7.506	58.686	1.426	7.506	58.686	2.614
5	1.229	6.467	65.153	1.229	6.467	65.153	3.153
6	1.115	5.869	71.022	1.115	5.869	71.022	2.609

Table 3 presents the Pattern matrix from factor analysis. It shows the loadings of each variable on the extracted components after rotation, helping to identify which variables are most strongly associated with each component.

Table 3 Pattern Matrix

	Component					
	1	2	3	4	5	6
S2	.858					
S1	.849					
S3	.835					
S4	.503					
U1		.801				
U4		.798				
U3		.622				
U3		.506				
B3			.970			
B2			.849			
B1			.799			
CO4				.812		
CO1				.798		
CO3				.734		
C02				.636		
FT1					.983	
FT2					.956	
W2						.891
W1						.733
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis						
Rotation Method: Promax with Kaiser Normalization						

Construct Reliability and Validity

A convergent validity test was conducted during the study's early phases. The loadings of the items, the average variance extracted (AVE), and the composite reliability (CR) were all critically examined in this study. Table 4 presents the findings. According to the above table, the loadings of the items above 0.6, meeting Hair et al. (2017)'s recommended threshold. According to Hair et al. (2009), the AVE threshold should be exceeded. The acceptable range for the AVEs in this investigation was between 0.557 and 0.756. Additionally, the CR value varied between 0.769 and 0.880, which is in line with the figure that Hair et al. (2009) recommended.

Table 4 Construct Reliability and Validity

	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability (rho_a)	Composite reliability (rho_c)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Brand-name consciousness	0.841	0.952	0.901	0.753
Conspicuousness	0.747	0.797	0.835	0.559
Female Temptation	0.935	0.936	0.969	0.939
Status-consumption	0.806	0.887	0.866	0.618
Need for Uniqueness	0.760	0.777	0.847	0.581
Willingness to pay	0.714	0.832	0.869	0.769

Once the construct reliability has been checked next step is to check the discriminant validity.

The hetero-monotrait (HTMT) correlation ratio was first presented by Henseler et al. (2016) as a cutting-edge method for evaluating the discriminant validity of structures in measurement models. An average HTMT score more than 0.85 indicates a potential issue with discriminant validity (Purwanto, 2021). As can be seen in table 5, there was no problem with discriminant validity because all of the HTMT values in this sample were just below the 0.85 threshold.

Discriminant Validity

Table 5 HTMT

	Brand-name Consci.	Conspicuousness	Female Temptation	Status-consumption	Uniqueness
Brand-name Consci.					
Conspicuousness	0.180				
Female Temptation	0.355	0.288			
Status-consumption	0.627	0.266	0.361		
Uniqueness	0.453	0.304	0.446	0.491	
Willingness to pay	0.504	0.157	0.371	0.465	0.528

This study uses the Fornell–Larcker analysis for discriminant validity as a reference. As shown in Table 6, all constructs exhibit sufficient or satisfactory discriminant validity (Fornell and Larcker, 1981), in which the square root of AVE (diagonal) is larger than the correlations (off diagonal) for all reflective constructs. However, many have criticized the Fornell–Larcker criterion by arguing that it is not justifiable to detect the lack of discriminant validity in general research scopes (Henseler et al., 2015).

Table 6 Fornell-Larcker criterion

	Brand-name Consci.	Conspicuous ness	Female Temptatio n	Status- consumptio n	Uniqueness	Willingnes s to pay
Brand-name Consci.	0.868					
Conspicuousn ess	0.188	0.748				
Female Temptation	0.343	0.257	0.969			
Status- consumption	0.554	0.245	0.351	0.786		
Uniqueness	0.376	0.215	0.382	0.374	0.762	
Willingness to pay	0.415	0.082	0.318	0.359	0.374	0.877

For the discriminant validity of measuring frameworks, another source of reference was the cross-loading values. According to Table 7, the loading of each measure (items on the measuring scale) on its underlying latent construct is greater than that of any other construct. Accordingly, as indicated in Table 7, these results provide strong evidence for reflecting the discriminant validity of measurement models and satisfy the conditions of the cross-loading evaluation.

Table 7 Cross-loading

	Brand-name Consci.	Conspicuousness	Female Temptation	Status-consumption	Uniqueness	Willingness to pay
B1	0.927	0.247	0.385	0.562	0.323	0.375
B2	0.813	0.058	0.259	0.391	0.430	0.381
B3	0.860	0.141	0.180	0.459	0.199	0.315
CO1	0.101	0.758	0.161	0.096	0.133	-0.039
CO2	0.263	0.813	0.265	0.392	0.132	0.097
CO3	0.041	0.663	0.141	0.034	0.269	0.064
CO4	0.075	0.749	0.161	0.069	0.152	0.104
FT1	0.322	0.237	0.968	0.329	0.357	0.318
FT2	0.341	0.261	0.970	0.351	0.384	0.299
S1	0.398	0.161	0.245	0.777	0.290	0.318
S2	0.405	0.193	0.152	0.769	0.324	0.251
S3	0.365	0.197	0.213	0.756	0.320	0.347
S4	0.524	0.216	0.388	0.840	0.280	0.246
U1	0.198	0.131	0.314	0.169	0.784	0.231
U2	0.316	0.215	0.247	0.364	0.695	0.324
U3	0.388	0.207	0.343	0.363	0.821	0.326
U4	0.237	0.101	0.244	0.253	0.742	0.265
W1	0.432	0.035	0.331	0.359	0.301	0.934
W2	0.266	0.134	0.204	0.255	0.383	0.815

Structure Model Analysis

Smart PLS has been used for the analysis purpose figure 2 shows the diagram; furthermore, the direction of the hypotheses put forth in the framework determines the arrows that connect the

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study's components. To confirm that the research construct has a causal effect, single-headed arrows are employed. Additionally, the standardised estimate for the structural model in this report is explained in Figure 2, which displays the factor loading for every item.

Figure 2 Smart PLS Standardized Result

Table 8 Path Coefficients

	Beta Value	Sample mean (M)	Standard deviation (STDEV)	T statistics (O/STDEV)	P values
Brand-name Consci. -> Female Temptation	0.144	0.141	0.058	2.485	0.013
Conspicuousness -> Female Temptation	0.142	0.148	0.067	2.120	0.034
Female Temptation -> Willingness to pay	0.318	0.323	0.052	6.059	0.000
Status-consumption -> Female Temptation	0.146	0.152	0.062	2.361	0.018
Uniqueness -> Female Temptation	0.243	0.246	0.062	3.946	0.000

Table 8 shows the study’s effects using the Smart PLS Structural Equation Model (SEM). The table 8 demonstrates the relationship between the path coefficients, standard deviation (STDEV), t-statistics, p-value and construct outcome. The result shows that conspicuousness (Beta value = 0.142; t value = 2.120; p-value = 0.034) directly effects the female temptation during selection of premium personal care products therefore hypothesis 1 is supportive. Hypothesis reported positive relationship status consumption (Beta value = 0.146; t value = 2.361; p-value = 0.018) and effects the female temptation during selection of premium personal care products. Brand-name consciousness (Beta value = 0.144; t value = 2.485; p-value = 0.013) has a positive relationship with effects the female temptation during selection of premium personal care products, accepting the hypothesis 3. Hypothesis 4 reinforced the projected relationship between need for uniqueness (Beta value = 0.243; t value = 3.946; p-value = 0.000) and effects the female temptation during selection of premium personal care products. Lastly, a strong relationship between the female temptation during selection of

premium personal care products and willingness to pay a premium (Beta value = 0.318; t value = 6.059; p-value = 0.000) supporting the hypothesis 5.

Table 9 Summary of R²

	R-square	R-square adjusted
Female temptation during selection of PPCPs	0.230	0.217
Willing to pay a premium	0.101	0.097

Table 9 displays the squared multiple correlations (R²) result, which suggests that the hypothesised model explained statistically significant variance for the endogenous variables. The squared multiple correlations (R²) coefficient for latent variables was tested to examine the variance of the latent variables, in accordance with the model.

CONCLUSION

The study on female temptation during the selection of premium personal care products reveals significant insights into consumer behaviour and decision-making processes. Females are often influenced by a combination of factors including conspicuousness, status, brand name consciousness and uniqueness of the products. The allure of premium personal products often heightened by the promise of superior efficacy, luxurious experiences, and the status associated with high-end brands.

The study highlights that temptation plays a crucial role in the willingness to pay a premium price, driven by the desire for status, enhance personal image, and the perceived value of the products. Marketing strategies that tap into these emotional and psychological triggers are likely to be more effective in attracting female consumers to premium personal care products. Moreover, the research suggests that while price sensitivity exists, it often overshadowed by the perceived benefits and the emotional gratification derived from using premium personal care products. This indicates that female consumers are willing to invest in the products that they believe will contribute to their self-esteem, status and overall well-being.

Overall, the study underscores the importance of understanding the underlying motivation and temptations that drive female consumers towards premium personal care products. Companies in the industry can leverage these insights to refine their marketing strategies, product offerings, and brand positioning to better meet the desires and expectations of their target audience.

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